

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CONSUMER DECISIONS IN USING THE GOJEK APPLICATION WITH GO-FOOD FEATURES IN BANJARMASIN CITY

Minarti Limantara 1, Laila Refiana Said 2

^{1,2} Universitas Lambung Mangkurat, Banjarmasin, Indonesia

Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received May 05, 2024 Revised May 10, 2024 Accepted May 25, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Price, promotion, culture, individual, social and consumer decisions.</p>	<p>This study aims to analyze the factors of price, promotion, culture, individual and social influence simultaneously (together) on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food Feature Go-Jek application in the city of Banjarmasin. The research method is an explanatory research. The sample size was taken using the Slovin formula and the results were 100 respondents (rounded up to represent the total population). The sampling technique used the purposive sampling method. The purposive sampling method is a sampling technique with certain considerations. The analysis technique uses multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 21.0 for windows. Based on the results of the research and analysis obtained, it can be concluded that the price, promotion, culture, individual, and social factors simultaneously (together) have a significant effect on consumer decisions in the use of the go-food feature go-food application in the city of Banjarmasin. The price factor partially has no significant effect on consumer decisions in using the go-food feature go-food application in the city of Banjarmasin. Promotion factor partially has no effect and significance on consumer decisions in using the go-food feature go-food application in the city of Banjarmasin. Cultural factors partially have no effect and significance on consumer decisions in using the go-food feature go-food application in the city of Banjarmasin. Individual factors partially have a significant effect on consumer decisions in using the go-food application feature of go-food in the city of Banjarmasin. Partial social factors have no significant effect on consumer decisions in the use of the go-food application feature go-food in the city of Banjarmasin.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

Corresponding Author:

Minarti Limantara

Universitas Lambung Mangkurat, Banjarmasin, Indonesia

Email: 2341217320016@ulm.ac.id

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries affected by internet developments. According to research results from We Are Social (2019:3), It was revealed that of the total 268.2

million people in Indonesia, 150 million of them have used social media. Thus, the penetration rate is around 56 percent. The research results, published on January 31 2019, had a research duration from January 2018 to January 2019. There was an increase of 20 million social media users in Indonesia compared to last year. The development of the internet followed by rapid developments in the telecommunications sector, especially cellular telephone devices, has had a significant impact on consumer behavior (Suryani, 2013).

Go-Food is a service feature provided by Go-Jek which provides food delivery services in Indonesia. Indonesia is a country that has and serves various culinary products, both with Indonesian and modern tastes, following current trends. To date, more than 125,000 restaurants have become Go-Food partners and officially collaborate with Go-Food. Go-Food partners do not only consist of luxury restaurants but consist of small community businesses, such as street vendors, to food produced by the SME industry.

On the other hand, Go-Food is trying to act as a stimulus for consumer growth. This also functions as a solution to consumer problems found in market evaluations. One of the problems that arises in relation to food delivery services is the influence on people's mobility as consumers. The trend of city residents who have high mobility, limited time, and a high need for food can now be overcome with the existence of Go-Food. High service standards and accuracy in delivery service are always upheld to satisfy customers. This is done by Gojek through its Go-Food service as part of stimulating consumer growth. The Go-Food phenomenon that occurs among the public is due to the practicality that Gojek offers in food delivery services. Orders can only be made using a smartphone by opening the Go-Food feature in the Gojek application. This shows that there is ease in accessing or being reached by its users. Another phenomenon is that the Go-Food application, apart from being very easy for consumers, is also very helpful in terms of time efficiency and practicality for consumers. However, on the other hand, of course there is a negative for consumers, namely that more or less it will make people are lazier.

Based on the problems above, the author is interested in conducting research with the title "Analysis of Factors that Influence Consumer Decisions in Using the GOJEK Application with GO-FOOD Features in Banjarmasin City".

METHODS

This research is survey research, namely by taking samples from a population and using a questionnaire as a data collection tool. The main thing is that there is a hypothesis whose truth will be tested in this research, so the type of research used is explanatory research, namely research that explains the causal relationship between variables. -variables through hypothesis testing.

The population in this study was all residents of the city of Banjarmasin, totaling 700,870 people. The sample size was taken using the Slovin formula. The number of samples obtained was 100 respondents (rounded up to represent the total population). The

sampling technique uses a purposive sampling method. The purposive sampling method is a technique for determining samples with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2011: 78). The specified criteria are as follows:

1. The consumers who were respondents were the people of Banjarmasin city.
2. Consumers who were respondents were those who had used the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application more than once.

Data analysis technique using multiple linear regression analysis using the SPSS for Windows program.

A variable is anything that will be an object of observation in research in the form of a concept that has varying values. In this research, the independent variables will be revealed, namely price, promotion, cultural, individual and social factors and the dependent variable, namely consumer decisions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table Analisis Regresi Linier Berganda

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	7.271	2.435		2.986	.004
1 harga	.169	.087	.179	1.941	.055
promosi	-.002	.090	-.002	-.022	.983
budaya	-.105	.090	-.108	-1.164	.247
individu	.390	.092	.399	4.228	.000
sosial	.007	.092	.007	.072	.943

a. Dependent Variable: keputusan menggunakan aplikasi gojek fitur go-food

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Based on the calculation results of the SPSS program, the following results were obtained:

$$Y = 7.271 + 0.169X_1 + 0.002 X_2 + 0.105$$

Information :

- 1) Constant (α) = 7.271 shows the magnitude of the influence of all independent variables on the dependent variable. If the independent variables are constant, then the decision value using the Gojek application with the Gojek feature is 7,271.
- 2) The price coefficient value (b_1) = 0.169 shows that the price has a positive effect. If the price is better, it will increase the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application assuming other variables are constant or fixed.
- 3) The promotion coefficient value (b_2) = 0.002 shows that promotion has a negative effect on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Go-Jek application. The lower the promotion, the lower the influence on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Go-Jek application, assuming other variables are constant or fixed.
- 4) The cultural coefficient value (b_3) = 0.105 shows that culture has a negative influence on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Go-Jek application, the lower the culture, the lower the influence on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Go-Jek application, assuming other variables are constant or fixed.
- 5) The individual coefficient value (b_4) = 0.390 shows that the individual has a positive influence. If the individual is better, it will increase the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application assuming other variables are constant or fixed.
- 6) The social coefficient value (b_5) = 0.007 shows that social has a positive influence. If social is better, it will increase the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application assuming other variables are constant or fixed.

b. F test

In this research, to find the influence of the independent variables from the multiple linear regression equation together, it can be tested using the F test.

Table Uji F-test

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.111	5	7.222	5.203	.000 ^b
	Residual	130.479	94	1.388		
	Total	166.590	99			

a. Dependent Variable: keputusan menggunakan aplikasi gojek fitur go-food

b. Predictors: (Constant), sosial , harga, individu, budaya, promosi

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

From the table above, the Fcount value is 5.203, which is more than the Ftable value of 3.090 with a significance level of 0.000. The resulting significance value is smaller than 0.05. This means that price, promotion, cultural, individual and social variables simultaneously have a significant influence on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in Banjarmasin City.

c. t test

Table t Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.271	2.435		2.986	.004
	harga	.169	.087	.179	1.941	.055
	promosi	-.002	.090	-.002	-.022	.983
	budaya	-.105	.090	-.108	-1.164	.247
	individu	.390	.092	.399	4.228	.000
	sosial	.007	.092	.007	.072	.943

a. Dependent Variable: keputusan menggunakan aplikasi gojek fitur go-food

Source: Primary data processed in 2023

Based on the calculation results of the SPSS program, the t-test hypothesis testing is as follows:

- a. The influence of the price variable (X1) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

From the results of statistical calculations using SPSS 21.0 in table 5.35 for the price variable (X1), a t value of 1,941 is obtained which is greater than the t table value of 1,661 with a significance level of 0.055. The resulting significance value is greater than 0.05. This means that the decision variable using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained without being influenced by the price variable (X1). So it can be concluded that the price variable (X1) with product price affordability (X1.1), price suitability to product quality (X1.2), and discounts (X1.3), partially have no significant effect on the decision to use the Go-feature Gojek application. -food in the city of Banjarmasin.

- b. The influence of the promotion variable (X2) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

From the results of statistical calculations using SPSS 21.0 in table 5.35 for the promotion variable (X2), a t value of -002 is obtained, which is smaller than the t table value of 1,661 with a significance level of 0.983. The resulting significance value is greater than 0.05. This means that the decision variable to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained as having a negative effect by the promotion variable (X2). So it can be concluded that the promotion variable (X2) with go-pay delivery promo (X2.1), free additional menu (X2.2), and discount (X2.3), partially has no influence and significance on the decision to use the Gojek application feature go-food in the city of Banjarmasin.

- c. The influence of cultural variables (X3) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin

From the results of statistical calculations using SPSS 21.0 in table 5.35 for the cultural variable (X3), a t value of -1,164 is obtained, which is smaller than the t table value of 1,661 with a significance level of 0.247. The resulting significance value is greater than 0.05. This means that the decision variable to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained and not influenced by the cultural

variable (X3). So it can be concluded that the cultural variable (X3) with cultural shifts (X3.1), geographical area (X3.2), and social class (X3.3), partially has no influence and significance on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.

- d. The influence of individual variables (X4) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin

From the results of statistical calculations using SPSS 21.0 in table 5.35 for the individual variable (X4), a t value of 4,228 is obtained which is greater than the t table value of 1,661 with a significance level of 0.000. The resulting significance value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the decision variable using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained by the influence of individual variables (X4). So it can be concluded that individual variables (X4) with work and social environment (X4.1), lifestyle (X4.2), and personality (X4.3), partially have a significant effect on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in Banjarmasin city.

- e. The influence of social variables (X5) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

From the results of statistical calculations using SPSS 21.0 in table 5.35 for the social variable (X5), a t value of 0.072 is obtained which is smaller than the t table value of 1.661 with a significance level of 0.943. The resulting significance value is greater than 0.05. This means that the decision variable using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained without being influenced by social variables (X5). So it can be concluded that the social variables (X5) with the reference group (X5.1), family (X5.2), and role and status (X5.3), partially have no significant effect on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in Banjarmasin city.

5. Discussion of Research Results

1. The influence of the price variable (X1) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

The decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained without being influenced by the price variable (X1). So it can be concluded that the price variable (X1) with product price affordability (X1.1), price suitability to product quality (X1.2), and discounts (X1.3), partially have no significant effect on the decision to use the Go-feature Gojek application. -food in the city of Banjarmasin. This is because although most respondents think that before buying a product, consumers will look at the price first, there are respondents who ignore the price because the practicality of using go-food without having to go out to the outlet is commensurate with the price on the Go-Jek application, the Go-Food feature food that is more expensive than the price at the original outlet. So price variables with indicators of product price affordability, price suitability for product quality and discounts do not influence the decision to use the go-food feature in Banjarmasin City.

The results of this research are in accordance with research conducted by Munawaroh (2019) which states that the price factor does not influence consumer decisions in choosing to use Go-Jek services among STIE Indonesia Banjarmasin students. However, the results are different from research conducted by Lutfiah (2019) which states that price factors can influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application.

2. The influence of the promotion variable (X2) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

The decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained as not being influenced by the promotion variable (X2). So it can be concluded that the promotion variable (X2) with go-pay delivery promo (X2.1), free additional menu (X2.2), and discount (X2.3), partially has no influence and significance on the decision to use the Gojek application feature go-food in the city of Banjarmasin. This can be interpreted that the lower the consumer's perception of the promotion, the weaker it will encourage consumers to make decisions using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.

The results of this research are different from research conducted by Lutfiah (2019) which states that promotional factors can influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application.

3. The influence of cultural variables (X3) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin

The decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be explained partially and not influenced by cultural variables (X3). So it can be concluded that the cultural variable (X3) with cultural shifts (X3.1), geographical area (X3.2), and social class (X3.3), partially has no influence and significance on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin. Consumers feel that the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application is not based on background cultural factors such as environmental influences, trends in society and social class. This is because consumers choose to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application, not because of the influence of shifts in culture, geographic region or social class. Consumers consider the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application to be based on their needs and the convenience it offers.

The results of this research are different from research conducted by Lutfiah (2019) which stated that cultural factors can influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application.

4. The influence of individual variables (X4) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin

The decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be partially explained by the influence of individual variables (X4). So it can be concluded that individual variables (X4) with work and social environment (X4.1), lifestyle (X4.2), and personality (X4.3), partially have a significant effect on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in Banjarmasin city.

The results of this research are in accordance with research conducted by Lutfiah (2019) which states that individual factors can influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application.

5. The influence of social variables (X5) on the decision to use the Go-Food feature Gojek application (Y) in the city of Banjarmasin.

The decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application can be explained partially and not influenced by social variables (X5). So it can be concluded

that the social variables (X5) with the reference group (X5.1), family (X5.2), and role and status (X5.3), partially have no significant effect on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in Banjarmasin city. Consumers who decide to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application consider this decision not to be based on social influence, whether the influence of friends, family or the environment. Apart from that, it could be that not many consumers' friends, family or the environment around them use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application, so they choose it because of the influence of other factors.

The results of this research are in accordance with research conducted by Munawaroh (2019) which states that social factors have no influence on consumer decisions in choosing to use go-jek services among STIE Indonesia Banjarmasin students. However, the results are different from research conducted by Lutfiah (2019) which states that social factors can influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application.

6. The influence of price, promotion, culture, individual and social simultaneously on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.

Statistically, this test proves that price, promotion, cultural, individual and social variables simultaneously influence the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin. This means that the decision variable using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application (Y) can be explained as having a significant influence on price (X1) with elements of product price affordability (X1.1), price suitability with product quality (X1.2), and discounts. (X1.3), promotions (X2) with go-pay delivey promo elements (X2.1), free additional menus (X2.2), and discounts (X2.3), Culture (X2) with cultural shift elements (X3 .1), geographic region (X3.2), and social class (X3.3), individual (X4) with elements of work and social environment (X4.1), lifestyle (X4.2), and personality (X4. 3), and social (X5) with elements of reference group (X5.1), family (X5.2), and role and status (X5.3). So it can be concluded that the variables price (X1), promotion (X2), culture (X3), individual (X4), and social (X5) simultaneously have a significant influence on the decision to use the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis above, the following conclusions are proposed:

1. Workload influences the job satisfaction of KH Hospital employees. Mansyur Kintap. Subjective workload is related to the measurement used by someone to express feelings of being overworked, measures of job pressure and job satisfaction.
2. Price, promotion, cultural, individual and social factors simultaneously (together) have a significant influence on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.
3. The price factor partially has no significant effect on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.
4. Promotion factors partially have no influence or significance on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.
5. Cultural factors partially have no influence or significance on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.
6. Individual factors partially have a significant influence on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin.
7. Social factors partially have no significant effect on consumer decisions in using the Go-Food feature of the Gojek application in the city of Banjarmasin

REFERENCES

- Djarwanto P.S. 2008. *Statistik Induktif*. Yogyakarta : BPF.
- Ghozali, Imam. 2009. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*, Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- _____. 2011. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*, Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- _____. 2013. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*, Semarang : Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hawkins dan Mothersbaugh. 2007. *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy*. Irwin: McGraw-Hill.
- Herdiansyah. 2018. Tren Penggunaan Aplikasi Go-Food dalam Pemesanan Produk Ayam Olahan di Kecamatan Lowokwaru Kota Malang. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis*. Volume 2 Nomer 1.
- Kotler dan Armstrong. 2008. *Prinsip-Prinsip Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- _____. 2011. *Prinsip-Prinsip Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Kotler, Philip. 2005. *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Gramedia.

- _____. 2012. *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Kotler dan Hawkins. 2007. *Manajemen Pemasaran Perspektif Asia*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Kotler, Philip & Keller, Kevin Lane. 2007. *Marketing Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Lutfiah, Evi. 2019. Analisis Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Menggunakan Aplikasi Go-Jek Fitur Go-Food (Studi kasus Pada Sosial Fakultas Ilmu Tarbiyah dan Mahasiswa Jurusan Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Keguruan Universitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta). *Jurnal UIN Syarif Hidayatullah*.
- Munawaroh. 2019. Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Konsumen dalam Memilih Menggunakan Jasa Transportasi Online pada Mahasiswa STIE Indonesia Banjarmasin. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Akuntansi*. Volume 20 Nomer 1.
- Nurdiansyah. 2017. Pengaruh Kualitas Produk dan Harga Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Sepatu Olahraga Merek Adidas di Bandar. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Manajemen*.
- Pattinasarany, Ronny. 2009. *Pemasaran Strategi, Taktik dan Kasus*. Yogyakarta: Marknesis.
- Purwati. 2012. Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga dan Iklan Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian. *Jurnal Universitas Diponegoro Semarang*.
- Rachmawati Setyaningsih (2018), Analisis Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Pemanfaatan Go-Food (Studi Kasus Pada Mahasiswa UII)
- Setyaningsih. 2018. Analisis Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Perilaku Mahasiswa dalam menggunakan Go-Food di Kota Jambi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Media Sisfo*. Volume 14 Nomer 1.
- Stanton, William J. 2012. *Prinsip Pemasaran*, alih bahasa : Yohanes Lamarto. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Stephen dan Timothy. 2008. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Terjemahan: Diana Angelica, Ria Cahyani dan Abdul Rosyid. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Suardy, RR. Siti Munawaroh (2019), Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Konsumen Dalam Memilih Menggunakan Jasa Transportasi Online Pada Mahasiswa STIE Indonesia Banjarmasin.
- Sudjana. 2008. *Metode Statistika*. Bandung: Tarsito.
- Sugiyono. 2011. *Memahami penelitian kualitatif*. Bandung : Alfabeta.

- Supranto dan Nandan Limakrisna. 2007. *Perilaku Konsumen dan Strategi Pemasaran Untuk Memenangkan Persaingan Bisnis*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- Suryani. 2007. *Perilaku Konsumen Implikasi Pada Strategi Pemasaran*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- _____. 2013. *Perilaku Konsumen Implikasi Pada Strategi Pemasaran*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Swasta, Basu. 2000. *Manajemen Penjualan*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- Swasta dan Irawan. 1990. *Manajemen Pemasaran Modern*. Yogyakarta: Liberty.
- Tjiptono, Fandy. 2008. *Pemasaran Strategik*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- _____. 2008. *Pemasaran Strategik*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Umar, Husein. 2008. *Riset pemasaran dan perilaku konsumen*. Jakarta : Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Undang-Undang Nomor 40 Tahun 2007 tentang Perseroan Terbatas.